

Hyponatremia: Diagnostic Approaches and Management Strategies**Kamlesh Fatania****Assistant Professor, Department of General Medicine, Swaminarayan Institute of Medical Sciences & Research, Kalol, Gandhinagar****Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024****Corresponding Author: Dr. Kamlesh Fatania****Conflict of interest: Nil****Abstract:**

Hyponatremia is a common water balance disorder that often poses a diagnostic or therapeutic challenge. Therefore, guidelines were developed by professional organizations, one from within the United States (2013) and one from within Europe (2014). This review discusses the diagnosis and treatment of hyponatremia, comparing the two guidelines and highlighting recent developments. Diagnostically, the initial step is to differentiate hypotonic from nonhypotonic hyponatremia. Hypotonic hyponatremia is further differentiated on the basis of urine osmolality, urine sodium level, and volume status. Recently identified parameters, including fractional uric acid excretion and plasma copeptin concentration, may further improve the diagnostic approach. The treatment for hyponatremia is chosen on the basis of duration and symptoms. For acute or severely symptomatic hyponatremia, both guidelines adopted the approach of giving a bolus of hypertonic saline. Although fluid restriction remains the first-line treatment for most forms of chronic hyponatremia, therapy to increase renal free water excretion is often necessary. Vasopressin receptor antagonists, urea, and loop diuretics serve this purpose, but received different recommendations in the two guidelines. Such discrepancies may relate to different interpretations of the limited evidence or differences in guideline methodology. Nevertheless, the development of guidelines has been important in advancing this evolving field.

Keywords: cerebral edema, copeptin, vasopressin, urea, vasopressin receptor antagonist, osmotic demyelination syndrome.

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Introduction

Hyponatremia (serum sodium [SNa] <136 mmol/L) is a common water balance disorder that often poses a diagnostic or therapeutic challenge. [1] This may explain why management of hyponatremia is still suboptimal, as also recently illustrated by a hyponatremia registry. [2] Hyponatremia is not a disease but rather a pathophysiologic process indicating disturbed water homeostasis. [3] Therefore, hyponatremia should be further classified in order to provide directions for diagnosis and treatment. These classifications illustrate that hyponatremia is a very heterogeneous disorder. This has complicated clinical studies, because “the” patient with hyponatremia does not exist. Instead, the underlying disease that is complicated by hyponatremia usually characterizes patients with hyponatremia. [4,5] The most common causes of hyponatremia are the syndrome of inappropriate antidiuresis (SIAD), diuretic use, polydipsia, adrenal insufficiency, hypovolemia, heart failure, and liver cirrhosis (the latter two are often collectively referred to as “hypervolemic hyponatremia”). Although recent years have seen several developments in the diagnosis and

treatment of hyponatremia, the evidence base is still limited. To capture the current approach to hyponatremia, two sets of guidelines have been developed, one by professional organizations from within the United States (“United States guideline”) and one from within Europe (“European guideline,” in which the authors of this review participated). [6–9] The professional organizations involved in the United States guideline were Tufts University Office of Continuing Education and In 2 MedEd; the initiative was also supported by an unrestricted educational grant from Otsuka America Pharmaceutical. [9] The professional organizations involved in the European guideline were the European Renal Association–European Dialysis and Transplantation Association, the European Society of Endocrinology, and the European Society of Intensive Care Medicine. [6–8] The United States guideline refrained from using a quality-of-evidence scoring system due to the limited evidence. Instead, the guideline was on the basis of expert panel recommendations, which relied on a critical evaluation of relevant literature by the panel members. The European guideline did perform systematic reviews of the available

evidence using the Grading of Recommendations Assessment Development and Evaluation scoring system. Both guideline committees were interdisciplinary, and the European guideline was endorsed by the European societies of nephrology, endocrinology, and intensive care. [6–8] This brief review will compare the two guidelines to discuss the diagnosis and treatment of hyponatremia, while also highlighting recent developments. Because of the breadth of both guidelines, this review will focus on the salient features.

Pathogenesis

In contrast to sodium and glucose, urea raises osmolality but not tonicity because it has high-cell-membrane permeability. [5,6] This phenomenon also occurs with alcohols. A patient with hyponatremia in conjunction with uremia or severe ethanol intoxication may have high osmolality but low tonicity and therefore has an increased risk of cerebral edema.

Hyponatremia may be associated with normal or high tonicity. [5,6] Hyperglycemia translocates water from cells into extracellular fluid and causes hyponatremia simultaneously with hypertonicity; each 100-mg/dL increase in the glucose level decreases the serum sodium level by approximately 2 mEq/L. Retention of mannitol or irrigant solutions without sodium can cause isotonic or hypertonic hyponatremia. Pseudohyponatremia reflects a laboratory artifact that occurs in patients with severe hyperproteinemia or extreme hyperlipidemia, in which hyponatremia is associated with normal tonicity. Point-of-care devices are not subject to this laboratory artifact.

Water homeostasis depends on receptors residing along the anterior wall of the brain's third ventricle that respond to serum tonicity and angiotensin II by regulating water intake (thirst) and water excretion (release of vasopressin). [7] Vasopressin (antidiuretic hormone) is secreted by hypothalamic neurons in response to hypertonicity (osmotic stimulus) and decreased effective arterial blood volume (nonosmotic stimulus). Vasopressin promotes water retention by activating the vasopressin receptor 2 in the nephron's collecting duct, thereby inserting water channels in the apical membrane and increasing water permeability. Additional nonosmotic stimuli of vasopressin release include nausea, pain, acute stress (psychosis, exercise), postoperative state, and drugs such as narcotics and tricyclic antidepressants. [6,8]

According to the Edelman equation, serum sodium level $[Na^+]_s$ is approximated by the body's exchangeable sodium and potassium levels (Na_{ex}^+ and Ke^+ , respectively) divided by total body water: $[Na^+]_s \approx \frac{Na_{ex}^+ + K_{ex}^+}{\text{total body water}}$. Exchangeable sodium and potassium levels refer to the portion of their content (approximately 70%

and 85%, respectively) that is osmotically active; most nonexchangeable sodium resides in bone. The Edelman equation demonstrates that hyponatremia represents excess water relative to the exchangeable sodium and potassium levels. Hyponatremia may not develop with normal, decreased, or increased sodium content. [5,6,8,9]

Primary polydipsia is characterized by increased total body water. Hypovolemic hyponatremia (diarrhea) is characterized by reduced exchangeable sodium and potassium levels, with a smaller decline in total body water. Hypervolemic hyponatremia (heart failure) is characterized by an increased exchangeable sodium level with a larger increase in total body water. The syndrome of inappropriate antidiuresis (SIAD) is characterized by mildly reduced exchangeable sodium and potassium levels combined with increased total body water.

In patients with hypervolemic hyponatremia, reduced effective arterial blood volume results from pump failure (heart failure), decreased vascular resistance (cirrhosis), or arterial underfilling (nephrotic syndrome). [8] Cortisol deficiency (due to adrenocorticotropic hormone deficiency or panhypopituitarism) increases vasopressin release by stimulating the pituitary and by causing vasoplegia, which is characterized by hypotension and reduced systemic vascular resistance, thereby reducing effective arterial blood volume. Gain-of-function variants of the vasopressin receptor 2 gene account for nephrogenic SIAD. [6,8] In patients with acute kidney injury or chronic kidney disease (stage 3, 4, or 5), a decreased glomerular filtration rate and an inability to achieve a urine osmolality of less than 200 mOsm/kg to 250 mOsm/kg limit water excretion. [6,8]

Reduced solute intake, eg, 200 mOsm/d (beer potomania; normal diet, 600-900 mOsm/d), decreases water excretion to 4 L/d (at maximal urine dilution, 50 mOsm/kg). Hyponatremia typically does not develop unless water intake exceeds water losses from the kidneys and other routes. [5] Of the total cases of hospital-associated hyponatremia, 40% to 75% develop after hospitalization and are due to decreased water excretion from medications (opiates, vasopressin, oxytocin), pain, nausea, organ failure, or postoperative state combined with excessive administration of hypotonic fluids. [10] Thiazide-induced hyponatremia affects approximately 7% of hospitalized patients with hyponatremia and it presents with either hypovolemic hyponatremia or euvolemic hyponatremia that resembles SIAD. [9] Patients exhibiting the SIAD-like pattern of thiazide-induced hyponatremia may have a genetic predisposition to hyponatremia that is linked to a reduction in a prostaglandin transporter in the distal

nephron, which increases water reabsorption. [11] Potassium depletion contributes to the development of hyponatremia in all patients with thiazide-induced hyponatremia due to a reduction in exchangeable potassium level in the Edelman equation. [5,9]

In approximately 4% of people presenting with hyponatremia, water retention results from excessive water intake. Normal kidneys can excrete up to 1 L/h of water. [5,12] However, in patients with primary polydipsia, vasopressin may not be maximally suppressed (in those with a psychiatric disease or taking certain medications), contributing to water retention; median water intake was only 8 L/d, which is a fraction of the normal maximal level of water excretion. [12] Excessive intake of hypotonic fluids coupled with non-osmotic vasopressin secretion is the dominant pathogenesis of exercise-associated hyponatremia. Sodium loss due to sweat is a minor contributor. [13]

Symptoms of Hyponatremia

Manifestations of hyponatremia depend on the rapidity of development, duration, and severity of hyponatremia. Symptoms are more common in patients with acute hyponatremia (developing in <48 hours) than in those with chronic hyponatremia (developing over >48 hours) because of brain volume adaptation, which is a process that corrects hypotonicity-induced brain swelling. In a prospective, single-center study of 3784 patients in an emergency department, 166 (4.4%) presented with hyponatremia; each of the 3 forms of severity of hyponatremia, mild (serum sodium level of 130-134 mEq/L), moderate (125-129 mEq/L), and severe (<125 mEq/L), occurred in approximately one-third of the patients with hyponatremia. [1]

Symptoms of hyponatremia range from mild and nonspecific (weakness, nausea, headache) to severe and life-threatening (vomiting, somnolence, seizures, cardiorespiratory distress). [14] Acute severe hyponatremia can be associated with brain herniation, respiratory arrest, permanent brain damage, and death. Menstruating women are at a higher risk of having severe symptoms when they develop acute hyponatremia. Noncardiogenic pulmonary edema can occur in patients with hyponatremia due to acute water intoxication during endurance sports or intoxication with 3,4-methylene-dioxymethamphetamine ([ecstasy], which is an amphetamine used for recreational purposes), with hypoxemia worsening brain edema. Symptoms can progress suddenly and rapidly. [5,6,10,14]

Because of the skull's rigidity, brain swelling from hypotonicity-induced water entry into brain cells causes intracranial hypertension, which may reduce cerebral blood flow. [15] Prompt electrolyte

and water loss from brain cells occurs (known as rapid adaptation to hypotonic water entry) and can ameliorate swelling. Neither brain volume normalization is completed within approximately 2 days through the loss of organic osmolytes (eg, myoinositol, glutamate) and water from brain cells (slow adaptation). Correction of brain swelling accounts for less severe manifestations of chronic hyponatremia; these manifestations are caused by persistent hypotonicity and electrolyte or organic osmolyte depletion of brain cells. [6,10,14,16] In a prospective study of 298 patients with a serum sodium level of less than 125 mEq/L, including 96% with chronic hyponatremia, the symptoms were nausea (44%), vomiting (30%), confusion (30%), headache (27%), and seizures (5%) [17]; seizures most commonly occur in patients with extreme chronic hyponatremia (serum sodium level <110 mEq/L) and a history of seizures. [18]

Mild chronic hyponatremia in older people is associated with cognitive deficits, gait disturbances, and increased rates of falls and fractures. [19] An analysis of the prospective Rotterdam Study, 20 which included 5208 people aged 55 years or older (mean age, 70.3 years) with serum sodium levels at baseline, detected 399 patients with mild hyponatremia (mean serum sodium level, 133.4 mEq/L). The analysis reported a higher rate of prior falls at baseline in patients with hyponatremia compared with people with a normal serum sodium level (23.8% vs 16.4%, respectively; $P < .01$) and a higher rate of incident nonvertebral fractures over 7.4 years of mean follow-up in patients with hyponatremia than in people without hyponatremia (23.3% vs 17.3%, respectively; $P < .004$). [20] Hyponatremia has been identified as a secondary cause of osteoporosis and bone fractures with risk increasing with severity of hyponatremia. [21,22] Basic research studies show that a low sodium level enhances bone resorption and inhibits osteogenesis. [22] Brain volume adaptation to hyponatremia increases the risk of osmotic demyelination, a rare but serious neurological condition. [5,23] A national study from Sweden [24] identified only 111 patients with osmotic demyelination over 14 years. Osmotic demyelination results from overly rapid correction of chronic hyponatremia, primarily after daily correction of the serum sodium level by greater than 12 mEq/L, but rarely after correction by 10 mEq/L or less. [23] Osmotic demyelination involves the central pons but often extends into extrapontine structures, which are areas of the brain with both gray and white matter. Depletion of organic osmolytes predisposes individuals to astrocyte injury, disruption of the blood-brain barrier, and myelinolysis after the osmotic stress of overly rapid correction of chronic hyponatremia. [5,23]

Similar to animal studies, clinical observations suggest that azotemia protects from osmotic demyelination. [25-27] characteristically, a biphasic pattern evolves in which the treatment of patients with hyponatremia initially improves neurological manifestations, but is followed by symptoms of myelinolysis. Symptoms of myelinolysis occur approximately 1 day to 7 days after overly rapid correction of chronic hyponatremia; can be temporary, permanent, or progressive; and consist of hyperreflexia, pseudobulbar palsy, parkinsonism, locked-in syndrome, quadriplegia, and death. [23] Two weeks to 4 weeks after overly rapid correction of chronic hyponatremia may elapse before manifestations are apparent on brain magnetic resonance imaging consisting of hyperintense T2-weighted images. [23] Risk factors for osmotic demyelination include extreme chronic hyponatremia (serum sodium level <110 mEq/L), alcohol use disorder, liver disease or transplant, potassium depletion, and malnutrition. [5,16,23]

General approach to treatment

A cutoff of 48 hours is usually used to differentiate acute from chronic hyponatremia. This classification is useful because acute and chronic hyponatremia may be complicated by different neurologic conditions. Acute hyponatremia can cause cerebral edema when cells have insufficient time to adapt to the hypotonic extracellular environment. In chronic hyponatremia brain cell adaptation has occurred and, in this setting, an acute increase in extracellular tonicity induced by treatment can cause osmotic demyelination syndrome (ODS). [28,29] Therefore, for each patient with profound hyponatremia ($\text{SNa} < 125$ mmol/L), it is useful to consider whether cerebral edema or ODS should be suspected. This automatically leads to the often heated debate on optimal correction rates in hyponatremia. [30] Both guidelines reached consensus that the limit (not the goal) should be around 10 mmol/L per day for both acute and chronic hyponatremia. Of note, the United States guideline recommends a lower limit of 8 mmol/L per day if there is a high risk of ODS (e.g., in patients with hypokalemia, alcoholism, malnutrition, or liver disease). [9] In response to these recommendations, Adrogue and Madias proposed even more conservative limits of 6–8 mmol/L per day regardless of duration or symptoms. [11] Although we agree that this is likely to be both sufficient and safe, the data to support this are still limited. It is of interest to see how over the years the recommended correction rates have gradually become more conservative (with recommended correction rates as high as 20 mmol/L per day around 1990). [31] A subject directly related to correction rates is overcorrection. Both guidelines recommend frequent monitoring of

SNa during the active correction phase (i.e., all treatments except fluid restriction). An aspect that was overlooked by both guidelines is that the measurement of SNa may not offer the precision required for this monitoring. Tormey et al. calculated the so-called “reference change value” for SNa using a common analyzer and demonstrated that only changes in $\text{SNa} \geq 4$ mmol/L were certain to be real. [12] If overcorrection is detected, both guidelines used different criteria for when to relower SNa: when initial SNa was <120 mmol/L (United States guideline) or when limits are exceeded. Both guidelines recommend hypotonic fluids or desmopressin for relowering SNa. A combination of hypotonic fluids and desmopressin may be required for treating overcorrection in hypovolemic hyponatremia, because a persistent water diuresis may ensue after correction of hypovolemia. [32] Experimental data indicate improved outcomes with reinduction of hyponatremia after rapid overcorrection. [33] Another point that merits discussion is the consistent association of hyponatremia with worse outcomes. [34,35] This may indicate that hyponatremia has adverse effects beyond the classic neurologic symptoms. [36,37] However, in the absence of randomized intervention studies indicating that correction of hyponatremia improves outcomes, it remains unclear whether these associations are causal. [5]

Treatment of Acute Hyponatremia

Several settings predispose to acute hyponatremia, especially if combined with increased free water intake. [38] Among others, these include the postoperative period, exercise, and the use of 3,4-methylenedioxymethamphetamine (“Ecstasy”), haloperidol, thiazide diuretics, desmopressin, oxytocin, or intravenous cyclophosphamide. [39,40] A specific situation is the use of irrigants (glycine, sorbitol, mannitol) during transurethral or hysteroscopic procedures. Although absorption of the irrigants glycine and sorbitol may cause hypotonic hyponatremia, the degree of hypotonicity and therefore the risk of cerebral edema depend on the type of irrigant and the time course in osmolar shifts. [41,42] In contrast, mannitol causes hypertonic hyponatremia without a risk for cerebral edema. In daily practice, the distinction between acute and chronic hyponatremia is difficult, because the time in which hyponatremia developed is usually unknown. The United States and European guidelines approached this challenge differently. The United States guideline adhered to acute versus chronic hyponatremia, but did subdivide acute hyponatremia on the basis of the presence of severe or mild-to-moderate symptoms [9] The European guideline based its recommendations primarily on the presence and severity of symptoms rather than on duration. [7]

Both guidelines recommend hypertonic saline (typically 3% NaCl) for acute or symptomatic hyponatremia. [7,9] Hypertonic saline is an effective and potentially life-saving treatment for cerebral edema due to hyponatremia, as the high extracellular sodium concentration immediately removes water from the intracellular space. In patients with hypervolemic hyponatremia, hypertonic saline may be combined with loop diuretics. [9] The required volume of hypertonic saline to reach a predefined increase in SNa can be estimated using the Adrogé–Madias or Barsoum–Levine formulae. [42,43] Although predictions with these formulae are fairly accurate, [44] a switch toward giving hypertonic saline as fixed bolus has occurred in recent years. [45] No studies have systematically tested this approach, but there are a number of appealing aspects. First, especially in patients with cerebral edema, it is desirable to achieve a rapid partial correction in SNa. Second, a fixed bolus omits the need for calculations in a patient with an acute problem, limiting potential calculation errors. Third, bolus therapy limits the risk of overcorrection, which does occur commonly with a continuous infusion of hypertonic saline. [46] On the basis of these considerations; both guidelines recommend bolus therapy, albeit with slightly different specifications. [7,9] Recently, Ayus and colleagues reported their experience using a different protocol (500 ml 3% NaCl over 6 hours) in 64 patients with hyponatremic encephalopathy (SNa < 130 mmol/L and neurologic symptoms). [47] On average, this protocol increased SNa with 12 and 14 mmol/L in the first 24–48 hours, and improved symptoms without evidence of ODS. [47] However, the severity of hyponatremia (SNa frequently < 110 mmol/L) and the duration of symptoms suggest that some of these patients had chronic hyponatremia. If so, these correction rates would exceed currently recommended limits.

Treatment of Chronic Hyponatremia

Except for hypovolemic hyponatremia, the treatment of chronic hyponatremia relies on reducing free water intake and/or increasing renal free water excretion. Fluid restriction (< 1 L/d) is often the cornerstone of the therapy for chronic hyponatremia. [24] The urine to serum electrolyte ratio ($([UNa + \text{urine potassium concentration}]/SNa)$) indicates if the patient is in an antidiuretic or aquaretic phase, and can also help estimate the degree of fluid restriction required to increase SNa. [3,11,24,48] For patients with a ratio > 1 (indicating concentrated urine), < 500 ml fluid/d is recommended, which is difficult to adhere to. Winzeler et al. recently showed that in patients with SIAD fluid restriction is effective in 59% of patients. Predictors of nonresponse were a $UNa \geq 130$ mmol/L and $UOsm \geq 500$ mOsm/kg.

This implies that in patients with chronic hyponatremia pharmacologic therapy is often required to increase renal free water excretion. This can be achieved by treatment with loop diuretics, urea, vasopressin receptor antagonists (“vaptans”), or demeclocycline.

The two guidelines diverge in their recommendations regarding pharmacologic therapy for SIAD and hypervolemic hyponatremia. This was the case especially for vaptans, which will therefore be discussed in more detail below.

Vaptans

Vaptans block vasopressin type 2 receptors in collecting duct principal cells and therefore induce aquaresis (for comprehensive review, see Berl, [49] Hoorn and Zietse, [50] Lechrich et al., [51] Rozen-Zvi et al., [51] and Greenberg and Verbalis [52]. Several vaptans were developed, including tolvaptan, satavaptan, lixivaptan, and conivaptan (which also targets vasopressin type 1a receptors). On the basis of their mechanism of action, vaptans are a logical and targeted therapy for hyponatremic patients with excess vasopressin. Indeed, several large clinical trials have shown that vaptans are clearly effective in increasing SNa in patients with hyponatremia due to SIAD, heart failure, or liver cirrhosis. [53,54] Both guidelines agree that there is no place for vaptans in patients with acute or severely symptomatic hyponatremia, for which hypertonic saline is the treatment of choice. [7,9] Still, it has been difficult to position vaptans in the therapeutic arsenal of chronic hyponatremia. [11,9, 55,56] On the other hand, improvement of symptoms has been shown with the use of vaptans. This includes improvements in some neurocognitive symptoms, [57] performance status in cancer patients, [58] dyspnea in patients with heart failure, [60] and ascites in patients with liver cirrhosis. [59] Therefore, in our view, an unresolved question with regard to the use of vaptans remains, of whether symptomatic improvement outweighs the risk of overcorrection, even if ODS is rare.

Urea

Both guidelines suggest an interesting alternative to vaptans for chronic hyponatremia due to SIAD, namely urea. [61] Urea induces an osmotic diuresis, thereby increasing renal free water excretion. Decaux and colleagues pioneered the use of urea in the 1980s for SIAD, but also for other forms of hyponatremia. [62,63] More recently, in 12 patients with SIAD, Soupart et al. compared the treatment with satavaptan to urea (both treatment periods 1 year) [64] Interestingly, both therapies had a similar efficacy and side-effect profile. Although urea does not prevent overcorrection, it may reduce the risk of the associated brain damage.

In a rat model of experimental SIAD, Gankam Kenge et al. compared the neurologic outcomes after overcorrection (approximately 30 mmol/L per day) with hypertonic saline, lixivaptan, or urea [65]. One specific disadvantage of urea used to be its palatability. This problem has been solved by developing a formulation in which urea is combined with sodium bicarbonate, citric acid, and sucrose (see European guideline for prescription [7]) and by the development of a commercially available urea powder drink mix (Ure-Na by Nephcentric).

Conclusions

Our impression is that the development of the United States and European guidelines has helped to standardize and improve the management of hyponatremia. The two guidelines are more often in agreement than in disagreement. The discrepancies are likely related to the interpretation of the limited evidence and the methodology used to draft the guidelines. [66] Nagler et al. evaluated all available international guidelines [67] on hyponatremia and analyzed how well they met the Appraisal of Guidelines for Research and Evaluation criteria they identified considerable variation in methodologic rigor in the development of guidelines, potentially explaining inconsistencies in recommendations. [68] Because hyponatremia is a heterogeneous disorder rather than a clear-cut disease, not all patients can be covered by guidelines. That said, which evidence does the field need for the coming years? First, it would be useful to evaluate if a combination of the traditional and newer diagnostic tests would improve not only diagnosis but also outcomes. Second, the approach of giving a bolus of hypertonic saline should be studied to address the optimal volume, whether this should be on the basis of (ideal) body weight, and how often it should be repeated to reach the desired increase in SNa. [69] Third, the role of vaptans in the treatment of chronic hyponatremia remains a logical focus. For example, it would be important to analyze whether the copeptin-based subtypes of SIAD respond differently to vaptans. Finally, studies analyzing the effect of a vaptan in comparison with another active treatment (rather than placebo) on patient-relevant outcomes (rather than SNa) are warranted.

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